

THE PHENOMENON OF EPONYMY IN THE LINGUISTIC SYSTEM OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

Azimova Anisa Abroriddinovna

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10002691>

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about reforms in the field of culture, art, music, theater art in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the history of theater art, the development of theater art, and the issues of creating a modern hero in theater art.

Keywords: art, culture, reform, hero, theater, ability, tradition, process management, consciousness, reflection.

Abstract: This article discusses what an eponym is, the place of eponyms in Uzbek linguistics, their origin, scope of study, structure, and types of meaning. The lack of extensive study of eponyms in the system of secondary names in Uzbek linguistics, in particular, the study of this issue in the medical field, and the fact that it was analyzed only in some articles, motivated the study of the problem.

In the course of research, we witness that eponymous units are widely and actively used in every direction of the medical field. The sufficiency of the basis for their study in linguistics is determined by the specific naming feature of such units, semantic system, formation factors, their connection with language economy, their importance in enriching the lexical system, etc. Key words: eponym, term-word and term compound eponym, medical eponyms, lexical-semantic system

INTRODUCTION

The word "eponym" is derived from the Greek language and consists of two parts: "epi" - "above, suffix" and "onym" means "name". Thus, an eponym is the name of a real or fictitious person, on the basis of which another word or phrase is created. The name or surname of an eponym is a people, a place and others, is a person who has become their term.

Language is such a unique gift given to man, its possibilities are very limitless. One of such possibilities can be said to express a certain concept through the name of its discoverer or the name of a place related to it, etc. Therefore, the linguistic phenomenon called eponym (from ancient Greek ἐπώνυμος - name giver, from Latin - heros eponimus) as a unique form of naming began to attract the attention of linguists in recent years. Eponyms are unique names that have become common nouns in a certain field of knowledge. Eponymous terms exist in various fields of science, and when studying their linguistic features, it is appropriate to research based on the concepts that make up their scientific essence .

Initially, a divine, legendary hero or a real person was known as an eponym, in whose honor any geographical object was named (city, river, mountain, etc.). For example, the city of Byzantium, according to legend, was founded by the ancient Greek hero Byzantium, who was called the son of the god Poseidon. Thus, Byzantium is the eponym of Byzantium, and through it the eponym of the Byzantine Empire.

The city name "Rome" is named after the legendary hero Romulus, Yekaterinburg - Empress Ekaterina on behalf of II; The term "Victorian era" was formed as an eponymous term after the name of Queen Victoria.

In linguistics, eponym is understood as a terminological phrase, one of its components is a noun. R. Nestmann emphasized that the need to define new phenomena is the reason for the

emergence of eponyms. represents the mental characteristics of the nation. The phenomenon of eponymy can be observed in various fields of science, and almost no aspect of society can be imagined without them, for example: geography (volcano, ocean), physics (Volt, Hers), chemistry (Samary, Mendeleev), literature (Bukharians, Khlestakovs), visual arts (watman, felt-tip pen), food places (sweet, napoleon) and others.

The peculiarity of eponymous terms is their connection with the names of our contemporaries and the names of scientists, political and public figures, inventors who lived in the past.

Consequently, the names of famous people become "monuments" of their time and become the value of a certain nation. For example, Aristotelianism, Pythagoreanism in philosophy; Sufism, Naqshbandism in Sufism; Ottomans, Samanis, Timurids and many other terms related to periodization reflect history, development and formation of scientific schools. Therefore, the active formation of eponymous terms occurs during the rapid development of a certain field of knowledge.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In terms of grammatical and structural features, eponymic terms are in the form of term-word and term-combination, and they are mainly 1) affix-less conjugation relation - Newton's law, Murad Bilding and medial - auxiliary connection (according to Blanc and chloromethylation). At this point, it should be said that the formation of an eponymic term has its own characteristics that arise on the basis of the laws related to the formation of a term. Obligatory components of eponymous terms are names, which remain one of the most complex and controversial problems arising in connection with the problem of semantics of eponymous lexicon.

Based on the sources, N.V. Novinskaya divides the names into monoreferential (less common), widespread names (for example, Mendeleev, Pushkin, Balzac) and multi-referential, common names (Tatyana, John, etc.) emphasized that it is necessary to distinguish two different meanings in them - the closest, official, linguistic meaning and the distant subjective (individual) encyclopedic meaning. We think that it is the encyclopedic meaning that often causes the names of scientists who lived in the past to be mentioned repeatedly and is the basis for the formation of eponyms. In particular, Hatti Baburi (Letter of Babur) is a treatise of Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur and the type of letter promoted in this treatise.

Here it can be said that the linguistic, formal meaning of anthroponym essentially corresponds to the definition of "a person's name or surname" and is asemantic in nature, not associated with concepts, has the meaning of a sign, but an eponym -terms have different semantic encyclopedic meanings. In general, eponyms formed in the language for certain purposes can be divided into two types of names depending on their encyclopedic meaning:

- terms formed on the basis of the names of persons who directly made a major or fundamentally important discovery, led a new scientific direction, school, etc.;
- terms that include surnames given to a new object/event/subject etc. in honor of a person.

There are several methods of formation of eponymous terms, one of the most common of which is related to the traditional attribution of physical measurement units to the names of scientists who discovered them.

Morphological formation of eponym-terms based on anthroponyms is related to the name of a certain scientist, public figure, and is carried out through specialized derivative morphemes. For example, young grammarians, Yassavism, Baburites. This refers to a certain amount of

information related to a certain person, the author of a scientific direction, a social phenomenon, etc.

In addition, in the world of science, there are many eponyms with content, whose content is mainly an anthroponym related to the teaching, theory, discovery of a certain researcher, doctor, inventor, etc., and a combination of units such as law, method, disease, syndrome. are formed: caesarean section, Down's syndrome, cancer.

It is known that in the secondary denomination, the function of giving a new name is performed by adding existing lexical tools. Secondary nomination is a resource of language economy, it is considered the renaming of an already known linguistic unit. From the examples given above, it becomes clear that eponym-terms are also a secondary nominative method and with its help general concepts and rules are clarified or help to be clarified.

Eponym began to appear as a linguistic term in various languages from the 80s of the XX century. Over time, the meaning of the word expanded, and the word eponym is the name of a method in science, in addition to the object to which the name of a person has passed; the name of the disease in medicine; inventions in technology; began to represent geographical features. From this period, linguistic and non-linguistic scientific views on the study of eponyms begin to take shape.

Nowadays, an eponym is not the name of the person who named the object or process, but the name of the object or process itself. The word "Eponym" now belongs to the group of "antonym", "synonym", "homonym", "paronym", "toponym" as a linguistic term. At the same time, the linguistic term "eponymy" means "formation of new words based on appropriate names".

Most of the eponyms are terms, and research works, dissertations, books, articles, as well as special dictionaries have been created dedicated to the problem of these terms-eponyms in world linguistics. For example, in the works of M. G. Blau, V. V. Vakhrameyeva, V. M. Volodina, E. A. Syuzina, S. G. Kazarina, V. V. Kolmakova, N. V. Novinskaya, V. N. Teliya, a number of issues such as theoretical issues related to eponymy, terminological apparatus, field eponyms, and formation factors were studied. If found, in the aspect of lexicography, references of S. B. Korolev and R. P. Samusyev, a dictionary edited by L. P. Churilov, dictionaries of V. D. Ryazantsev and E. M. Kakzanova were created.

N.W. Novinskaya calls eponyms full-fledged members of the terminological system and evaluates them as a potential source for the formation of terms with nominative value, pointing out their role in the transmission of scientific and technical information as a characteristic feature. . In the article of Y.E. Kosterina, N.V. Noting that Podolskaya defined eponyms as "a person whose name served to create any other name", in this regard, eponyms mean a person who has a unique name in the name of a concept, and the term eponym means terms made up of eponyms, i.e. It is emphasized that the structure of terms formed from names is understood. S.D. Shelov proposes to call special language signs that contain appropriate names in their lexical and syntactic structure as anthroponymic names.

The scientist, citing the expressions Cherenkov effect, Chebyshev's theorem, Planck's formula, etc. as examples, says that "the main word that syntactically expresses a general concept represents the most general concept of science and technology (that is, a general scientific or general technical term) and the nomenclature defining it is and the indicator syntactically turns it into a category of individual names," he explains.

N.S. Sharafutdinova, the terms that contain proper names are initially strongly associated with a specific name and, of course, are written with a capital letter, but gradually many of them become full members of the terminological system and grammatically formalized as common nouns.

From the above, it can be said that the denotation of terms with eponymous components is not a separate object related to a certain thing, on the contrary, their denotation is related to a scientific concept, and we consider this concept to be terms. In addition, the eponym as a component of the term differs from the proper name/name, as we noted above.

In our opinion, the eponymous component of terms cannot be replaced by another (Kalashnikov assault rifle, Alice in Wonderland syndrome...), when changing, the connection of the term with the eponymous part is lost, all this indicates the importance of eponymous components in the structure of the term, and such grounds for treating units as terms rather than names.

A.V. In her views, Superanskaya emphasizes the cultural importance of eponymous terms, their historical significance for the field of knowledge in which they operate, and the fact that they contain important information aimed at the development of ideas in a certain field.

CONCLUSION

During the research, we witnessed that eponymous units are widely and actively used in every direction of the medical field. The sufficiency of the basis for their study in linguistics is determined by the self-naming nature of such units, their semantic system, formation factors, their connection with language economy, their importance in enriching the lexical system, etc. This is probably why medical eponyms have attracted many linguists and a number of research works have been carried out. In particular, it was studied by many foreign linguists such as E.V. Varnavskaya, V.N. Gubin, G.A. Hakimova, T.F. Izvekova, E.V. Smirnova, T.D. Tatarenko, D.K. Kondratiev. In particular, in E.V. Varnavskaya's dissertation, the question of the place of medical eponyms in the language system and the factors of their formation; In the researches of V.N. Gubin, eponym-terms and their appearance, features of formation in cardiology, angiology, rheumatology; The role of eponyms in the German veterinary terminological system in G.A. Hakimova's research; In the works of T.F. Izvekova, E.V. Smirnova, the problems of comparative analysis of this phenomenon in the field of languages were raised.

The lack of extensive study of eponyms in the system of secondary names in Uzbek linguistics, in particular, the study of this issue in the medical field, and the fact that it was analyzed only in some articles, motivated the study of the problem.

References:

1. Bozorov Z.A International scientific and practical conference "Modern psychology and pedagogy: problems and solutions" "Imperial College London" 2021-2022. 165-169 б.
2. Bozorov Z.A. Essence, structure and functions of civil culture. International engineering journal for research & development. Published in Volume 6 Special Issue, January 2021 of IEJRD E-ISSN: 2349-0721, Peer Reviewed & Referred Journal.
3. Bozorov Z.A. The role of motivation, needs and interests in the formation of civil culture of future medical workers. ACADEMICIA an international multidisciplinary research journal.

ISSN: 2249-7137. Vol. 11, Issue 3, March 2021. Impact Factor: SJIF 2021 = 7.492 DOI: 10.5958/2249-7137.2021.00835.1

4. Bozorov Z.A. The system of formation of civic culture among students in higher educational institutions. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 01 (81), 455-458. Soi: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-01-81-81> Doi: https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS_Scopus_ASCC_3304. (2020).
5. Bozorov Zayniddin & Samandarova Gulnoz. (2020). Ideological movement of legends and traditions in the novel "Shaytanat" by Tohir Malik. Theoretical & Applied Science. 84. 1014-1016. 10.15863/TAS.2020.04.84.187.
6. Bozorova G. Concerning some pleonastic and tautological constructions // Центр научных публикаций (buxdu.uz). – 2021. – Т. 7. – №. 7.
7. Bozorova G. Tautology and pleonasm: synchronic and diachronic views // Конференции. – 2021.
8. Bozorova G. Z. Ortiqchalik tamoyilining jahon tilshunosligida organilishi // Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 945-951.
9. Bozorova Gulmira Zayniddinovna. Distinctive features of pleonasm in political speech // International scientific-online conference: Intellectual education technological solutions and innovative digital tools. Vol. 2 No. 14 (2023): - P. 168-174.
10. Kadyrovna A. M., Zayniddinovna B. G. Description of Events Which is Near to Pleonasm // Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity. – 2022. – Т. 5. – С. 281-285.
11. Samandarova G.Y. Socially conditioned meanings of paremas formed on the basis of the lexical spiritual group "insects". Gospodarka i innowacje. Volume: 22 | 2022. –P. 443-446.
12. Samandarova G.Y., Adizova N.I., Bozorova G.Z. Methods of Using Metaphorical, Pleonastic and Paremic Units in Uzbek Linguistics // Resmilitaris. Vol. 13 No. 2 (2023): Volume 13, Number 2, 2023. –P. 5560-5572
13. Samandarova, G. Y. (2021). Fundamentals of folk proverbs formed on the basis of the lexical spiritual group of insects. Current research journal of philological sciences, 2(05), 39–42. <https://doi.org/10.37547/philological-crjps-02-05-11>
14. Samandarova Gulnoz Yarashovna, & Zaripova Nilufar Juma's daughter. (2023, April 1). Some characteristics of uzbek paremas' formed on the basis of the lexical sentence group "insect" in the form of a compound sentence. International scientific conference " Innovative Trends In Science, Practice And Education", Munchen, (Germany). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7816423>
15. Бекишева Е. В. Формы языковой репрезентации гносеологических категорий в клинической терминологии: автореф. дис. ... доктор. филол. наук. Москва, 2007. -50 с. – С.24
16. Бозорова Г. З. Идеиная направленность сказаний и преданий романа "Шайтанат" Тахира Малика // Молодой ученый. – 2014. – №. 9. – С. 532-534.
17. Бозорова Г. Илмий нутқда учрайдиган айрим плеонастик бирликлар таҳлили // Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 327-331.

18. Бозорова Г.З. ОАВда учрайдиган плеонастик бирликларнинг лингвопрагматик хусусиятлари // Interpretation and researches. 2023. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/oavdauchraydigan-pleonastik-birliklarning-lingvopragmatik-hususiyatlari> (дата обращения: 10.04.2023).
19. Кербер Е.В., Шуйцева И.А. Особенности эпонимов в немецкой экономической терминологии// <https://cyberleninka.ru>
20. Смирнова Е. В. Структурно-семантический и лексикографический аспекты медицинской терминологии: дисс. канд. филол. наук. Ярославль, 2012. -256 с.
21. Старичёнок В. Д. Большой лингвистический словарь. – Ростов-на-Дону: Феникс, 2008. -811 с.

